
"Ecocriticism Meets Cinema: Peranbu Examines the relationship Between Nature and Society"

Madhumitha R¹

Mr. Joshua L², M.A., B.Ed.

M.A English, mmitha593@gmail.com, Don Bosco college (Co_Ed) Yelagiri Hills.

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Abstract

We always hear stories that make us feel good about life there are many stories left unheard by people because we never want to hear the story that will break our hearts into pieces and show the real nature of humankind. making nature a storyteller the film *Peranbu* directed by Indian Film Director Ram received many awards and appreciation for giving light to the hidden pages of human life by breaking all the stereotypical ideas that are shown in all other films and also in our society. Disability is a burden for all beings living on the earth. But for nature everyone is equal. nature travels together with us in every situation social opposition, likes, dislikes, and changes, and in combination with the intuition of a person with a disability, also the film explores how nature connects with human life and how the father tolerates all the things that happen in her life. This is one in which a father who gracefully handles a woman's natural transformation without male dominance is positioned as a father who considers the many girls in this world as a blessing rather than a burden. This paper aims to open the hidden stories that all humans should know and how *Peranbu* breaks all stereotypical ideas about society and gender.

Keywords: sexuality, Gender, Trauma, Society, nature, disability.

Everyone in the world needs physical and mental health without these two one cannot live peacefully. More than anything everyone wants to live independently without depending on others. But not all can live independently because life is not the same for all, especially people who are born with a disability and will face suffering throughout their lives also children who have both physical and mental disabilities will face lots of struggles in their lives. All the time they need someone to guide and they cannot do anything on their own and they completely depend on others. Even their

family members refuse to help them, they want to live life by keeping them aside, and many of them either kill them instead of taking care of a disabled person or leave them in a shelter or the middle of the street and leave them to look after their daily life. In this film, the director Ram in a different way that no one has seen and no one experienced before in this area also with the help of nature he connects his life situations to changes that occur in nature in this world by dividing nature into categories and relating them to the life struggles of the father who is an individual in this film story and the social situations that he faces, Ram has a different perspective in life that made this movie as unique in all the aspects. In view, he has told the film *Peranbu* in the view of the world that the changes in nature travel along with his life.

“Nature taught me that the anger, regret, complaints, revenge and all such emotions within me are so meaningless” Disability arises from one birth and he is born indifferent to some challenges but biologically this is the order of all the species. Most Indian films only focus on showing the good side of society and they only focus on things that are beautiful in the eyes of human beings but they never think that in the eyes of nature, everything in this world is beautiful. In this, film we can see how they are different and pitiful in every view from society, and parents and relatives have not changed yet. The writer of the film has very beautifully written the twelve types which are seen as episodes of nature while others consider them to be just disabled. how nature changes according to the individual's way of bringing up women with a disability, contrary to the view of others, the viewer has been informed through this film that most of the media, news, and movies do not see disabled people much, on the one hand, they think that it is a pity, otherwise their needs, hunger, sleep is a sign to live in this world they think that this world is enough for them. The changes in the body and especially the hormonal changes in women have revealed such individual natural changes as evolution. Generally, in all the movies, people with disabilities have been shown humiliated. The idea that these are the same among the audience is also ingrained in the audience's minds, but with some changes, they have also expressed their feelings through the film directed by AL Vijay and through the episodes of nature we can know how every person is different and flawed in some way in the creation of nature.

This film reveals how a differently abled girl grows up. Her mother after knowing that her child is affected by cerebral palsy. She immediately leaves her without saying a word because she finds difficulties in taking care of her child. After his wife's separation breaks him apart in heartbreak, he wants to live for his daughter here the gender stereotypes that society creates on men cannot take care of their children without depending on their mother. But here the father came on his own to take care of his disabled daughter depending on any other Life continues with twelve episodes. Relatives and social activists try to exclude both the father and his disabled daughter from the plays where they live because she makes different sounds when she feels the pain of his wound. the character of the father gets a good reception. The first half of the

story continues amidst the surrounding nature. At first, Amudavan is hated by Papa who lures her into the trap of love. Has also shown. For Papa's needs and protection, he looks for a female guard and they also don't go well. Amuthan's task of seeking shelter for the girl is shown seriously. Especially in Ram view of Amuthan's character and the incident of marrying one's wife and inviting her home, especially the character of Amuthan from Ram's point of view and the incident of marrying a man's wife and inviting him to his wife and inviting him to his home, although in a comical form, is seen to bring up his girl safely. At one point Amuthan admits her to an orphanage where she finds many more like her in different forms but Amuthan's search does not end Amuthan goes to work as a taxi driver for women where he meets a transwoman. But Amuthan never sees her as different in behavior and speech and falls in love. Amuthan was afraid that his daughter would be in danger if she joined them because of that, Amuthan beat Papa in the shelter, he gathered her and came out to protect her, without even looking at her self-respect, he goes to his wife who has gone to someone else. However, realizing that he can't do anything for Amuthan's life and his daughter's to make things right, both of them tries to end their life but in the end, nature makes them live for the reason that nature loves all being the world equally with huge amount love.

Conclusion

"Whenever I think my life is not good, I always think of perambu" We complain about everything though we have everything in our lives. Many lives are full of problems that cannot be solved by anything or anyone but even though they have obstacles at the end of the day they will express their feelings and emotions to others, in *perambu* its completely different the child with a disability in both mental and physical tries to express herself to the family and to the society that she also has all the feelings that other human has. We never think of the people who are disabled from their birth also having the same emotions that we have but, in our society, no one is ready to take care of those beings because we never experience the pain that they go through every single minute of their lives. And we never fulfill their needs both physically and mentally. Ram shows the darker side of the people who are affected by disabilities also equal to the normal person and he asks us to treat the abnormal thoughts that society has on disabled people. Like all other Indian films that show only things that are meant to be beautiful are the good things and good people but *perambu* comes out and teaches us there is hope in everything by showing where society cannot give shelter to the father with his disabled daughter but nature gives everything that they needed the things cannot give by the humans is hope but that also given by nature in this film. *Comparing oneself to others is brutal* this is the message this film tries to tell us when we stop comparing ourselves to others and accept ourselves and others as what they are we can also get *perambu (Eternal love)* at the end of our life.

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